

E-MAPPER: Energy-Efficient Resource Allocation for Traditional Operating Systems on Heterogeneous Processors

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Abstract

Energy efficiency has become a key concern in modern computing. Major processor vendors now offer heterogeneous architectures that combine powerful cores with energy-efficient ones, such as Intel P/E systems, Apple M1 chips, and Samsung’s Exynos CPUs. However, apart from simple cost-based thread allocation strategies, today’s OS schedulers do not fully exploit these systems’ potential for adaptive energy-efficient computing. This is, in part, due to missing application-level interfaces to pass information about task-level energy consumption and application-level elasticity.

This paper presents E-MAPPER, a novel resource management approach integrated into Linux for improved execution on heterogeneous processors. In E-MAPPER, we base resource allocation decisions on high-level application descriptions that user can attach to programs or that the system can learn automatically at runtime. Our approach supports various programming models including OpenMP, Intel TBB, and TensorFlow. Crucially, E-MAPPER leverages this information to extend beyond existing thread-to-core allocation strategies by actively managing application configurations through a novel uniform application-resource manager interface. By doing so, E-MAPPER achieves substantial enhancements in both performance and energy efficiency, particularly in multi-application scenarios. On an Intel Raptor Lake and an Arm big.LITTLE system, E-MAPPER reduces the application execution on average by 20% with an average reduction in energy consumption of 34%. We argue that our solution marks a crucial step toward creating a generic approach for sustainable and efficient computing across different processor architectures.

1 Introduction

With the introduction of Intel Alder Lake processors [27], Intel follows the trend of heterogeneous CPUs, similar to the processor design seen in Arm big.LITTLE [20] and Apple

M1 [4] for the domain of powerful x86 desktop computers and servers. Recently, AMD revealed that upcoming processor releases will also include heterogeneous versions [10, 35]. With this, all major processor vendors now include heterogeneous CPUs in their portfolio.

Heterogeneous CPUs typically combine a small number of high-performance cores with a larger number of energy-efficient ones on one System-on-Chip (SoC). High-performance cores offer higher single-thread performance at the cost of increased power consumption, while energy-efficient cores have lower single-thread performance but substantially reduce power consumption. This difference in execution characteristics requires revisiting strategies for resource management in modern operating systems.

The type of core to which an application thread is scheduled can significantly affect its performance. Beyond differences in single-thread performance among core types, some cores may support different instruction sets. For instance, the energy-efficient E-cores in Intel Alder Lake processors lack the AVX-512 extensions available in the P-cores [18]. However, to what extent an application can profit from high-performance cores depends on its characteristics. For memory-bound and I/O-bound applications, for instance, the performance gap between core types can be negligible.

User-level requirements on application importance must also be accounted for in resource allocation. For instance, a foreground application like a video player is typically more important than a background update. The OS should allocate high-performance cores to the video player, even if other applications might benefit from these cores. Moreover, application priorities can change dynamically; for instance, an update process becomes more critical if explicitly triggered by the user. Ideally, this priority change should be immediately signaled to the OS, allowing prompt core reassignment and faster response to user requests.

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Modern OS schedulers have begun addressing the challenges posed by heterogeneous cores. Windows 11 added support for the Intel Thread Director to manage process placement on different CPU core types [17, 26]. Similarly, Linux introduced the Energy-Aware-Scheduler (EAS) extension in version 5.0, which considers the individual core performance when assigning them to processes in Arm’s big.LITTLE systems [45]. In addition, the Linux community is working to enhance the default system scheduler with feedback from the Intel Thread Director [13, 42]. Intel Thread Director allows for better runtime decisions on where to allocate applications, as live characteristics of the application behavior are taken into account. However, these systems lack an API for applications to influence placement decisions beyond explicit core pinning. State-of-the-art strategies used in traditional operating systems rely on simple and fast heuristics, often resulting in unpredictable and suboptimal execution.

Optimizing the mapping of applications onto heterogeneous multi-core systems is a well-known problem in the embedded domain [60]. Solutions can be classified based on when the decision is taken, e.g., at compile-time, at runtime, or a combination of both (*hybrid*). Compile-time methods offer near-optimal mappings but lack adaptability to changing workloads, making them unsuitable for dynamic systems where workload changes are unpredictable. Runtime methods, in turn, consider the current system workload and generate mappings *on-the-fly* – at application launch or during its execution. Hybrid application mapping (*HAM*) approaches combine the benefits of both design-time and runtime methods [47]. *HAM* methods offload compute-intensive calculations to compile-time, generating a set of Pareto-optimal mappings for each application, and adapt these intermediate solutions to the current workload at runtime. Modern *HAM* approaches consider heterogeneous processors to optimize energy efficiency while meeting certain Quality of Service requirements [29, 32, 62, 66, 68].

Our work introduces E-MAPPER, a runtime system designed to efficiently manage applications on desktop systems, servers, and mobile devices equipped with heterogeneous processors. Drawing from the embedded systems domain, our approach generalizes from *HAM*-based approaches, expanding them to support the execution of both known and unknown applications – a scenario not commonly addressed in embedded systems. Moreover, E-MAPPER accommodates user-defined priorities and supports dynamic changes in core assignments at runtime in response to application triggers. In this paper, we also discuss the modifications that are necessary to effectively support applications in E-MAPPER. Specifically, we detail how we adapted application models such as OpenMP, Intel Thread Building Blocks, and TensorFlow for efficient utilization in an OS that integrates E-MAPPER. Furthermore, we explain how E-MAPPER can automatically

learn and predict the application behavior at different configurations – a feature that is crucial to efficiently manage a wide variety of applications.

To our knowledge, E-MAPPER is the first system capable of semi-automatically managing applications with dynamic properties on heterogeneous processors while accounting for user requirements and system triggers. E-MAPPER aims to fill important gaps in modern operating systems, offering better system utilization, improved system performance, reduced energy consumption, and enhanced user experience. Our evaluation shows that E-MAPPER could reduce the energy consumption by 34 % and the execution time by 20 % over all applications measured on the Arm Odroid XU3-E board and the Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides background on heterogeneous processors, their benefits, and associated challenges. Section 3 presents the design of E-MAPPER, followed by Section 4 outlining the resource allocation approach and Section 5 detailing the runtime refinement of application configurations. Section 6 presents the evaluation of E-MAPPER. In Section 7 we discuss other solutions to the scheduling problem on heterogeneous CPUs, and Section 8 concludes our work.

2 A Case for Heterogeneity

Heterogeneous computing has become mainstream in the last years. Various types of heterogeneous systems, including CPU-GPU, CPU-FPGA, CPU-SmartNIC, and CPU-ASIC combinations, have their individual strengths and weaknesses as well as their own scaling and management challenges. In this work, however, we focus on heterogeneous processors where different core types, all running the same Instruction Set Architecture (ISA), are combined on one socket or System-on-Chip (SoC).

2.1 Heterogeneity in one Processor

Heterogeneous processors have long been used in mobile and embedded devices. The Arm big.LITTLE architecture was the first commercial design for such processors, consisting of two tightly connected islands of processors – one island contains one or many high-performance cores, and the other contains one or many energy-efficiency cores [34]. The high-performance (big) cores feature high single-thread performance and operate at a higher power envelope. The energy-efficient (LITTLE) cores, on the other hand, feature much lower single-thread performance at a lower power envelope. The big.LITTLE architecture was later extended by Arm in the DynamIQ design, allowing more flexible configurations and more core types [64]. For instance, the recent DynamIQ Shared Unit-120 [1] allows combining up to three different core types in a single processor.

In 2020, Apple released their M1 chip, which is based on Arm and uses the big.LITTLE approach with two types of

cores on one socket. The Apple M1 chip features one island with P-cores, equivalent to Arm’s big cores, and another island with E-cores, equivalent to Arm’s LITTLE cores. Later versions of the M1 chip, as well as the M2 and M3 chips, continue this design with varying combinations of P and E-cores.

A similar design is found in modern Intel x86 CPUs, such as the Alder Lake CPUs released in 2021 and the latest Raptor Lake CPUs released in 2022. In Core i5 versions and higher, these CPUs also feature a two-island design with P-core and E-core islands, following an approach similar to the Arm big.LITTLE architecture.

2.2 Benefits of Heterogeneous Processors

In the following, we discuss what trade-offs are opened up by heterogeneous processors.

Trading Performance against Energy. Modern processors, especially high-performance CPUs, have high static power consumption due to significant leakage resulting in less energy proportionality when scaling frequencies and voltages. Consequently, applications that cannot leverage the full single-thread performance of individual cores waste considerable energy on high-performance cores. This is typical for memory and I/O-bound applications. For such applications, energy-efficient cores with less static power are more suitable. By combining powerful and energy-efficiency cores in one socket, operating systems can decide at runtime where to run applications.

Trading Performance against Space. High-performance P-cores on modern Intel Raptor Lake processors require significantly more space on the die than the energy-efficient E-cores, even though the number of E-cores is larger than that of P-cores. This creates interesting trade-offs for chip designers aiming to produce processors tailored for certain workloads, such as CPUs with many E-cores for I/O-heavy applications. However, these tailored systems can only be truly leveraged by operating systems that are aware of application characteristics and can balance the allocation of P-cores and E-cores effectively.

2.3 Challenges of Heterogeneous Processors

To illustrate the performance-energy trade-off and how it varies from application to application consider the plot in Figure 1. The figure shows different configurations for two applications from the NAS Parallel Benchmark suite on an Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K. For *ep.C* (Figure 1a), there is a smooth gradient towards the upper right corner, both in terms of execution time and energy, indicating it runs well on both core types and scales with increasing core counts. Conversely, *mg.C* (Figure 1b) shows degraded performance and energy consumption on a heterogeneous core combination. Instead, this application performs much better on homogeneous configurations with a low overall core count.

Figure 1. Performance and energy consumption of two applications on an Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K with varying configurations. The x-axis refers to E-cores used, the y-axis to P-Hyperthreads. Each dot represents an application configuration with its thread distribution across P and E-cores. The dot size reflects the total execution time, and the color indicates energy consumption (red for higher consumption). Configurations highlighted in green are utilized by E-MAPPER.

Traditional system schedulers do not account for these differences. Moreover, there is no interface for applications to *inform* the operating system about their workload characteristics. E-MAPPER addresses this by configuring applications to use only (near-)optimal configurations, highlighted in green in Figure 1. For instance, E-MAPPER will never execute *mg.C* in the less efficient red configurations in the upper right corner, even if executing alone. On the other hand, *ep.C* can use the upper right configuration when controlled by E-MAPPER, as this configuration has benefits under certain circumstances. All this information is communicated within the E-MAPPER system using a well-defined interface.

3 E-MAPPER Design

This section details the E-MAPPER system’s architecture and the various application types it supports. Figure 2 provides an overview of our approach, divided into design time and execution time components. At design time, a high-level application description file containing the application *operating points* is created. Each operating point represents a combination of application configuration, specific hardware resource allocation, and non-functional characteristics such as expected utility (e.g. instructions per second or transactions per second) and average power consumption (⊙). This characterization of operating points can be done through various methods, from sophisticated design-space exploration using models, traces, and static analysis [12, 23, 37] to simple measurement-based resource annotations.

The core part of E-MAPPER lies in its execution time management approach. During this phase, E-MAPPER selects one

Figure 2. Overview of the E-MAPPER application management approach and system design.

of the available operating points for each managed application from the provided application description files (2), optimizing a user-selected global optimization target. For each application, E-MAPPER allocates corresponding hardware resources of the heterogeneous processor and reconfigures the applications accordingly (3 + 4). The resource allocation process considers runtime demands of applications and users, optimizing resource usage, application performance, and overall system energy consumption.

3.1 The E-MAPPER System Architecture

E-MAPPER includes three main components to interoperate with the operating system and client applications: (1) the E-MAPPER resource manager, (2) a shared library (libMapper) for application-level integration, and (3) application descriptions files. The system design is outlined on the right of Figure 2.

There is a single instance of the central resource manager and as many instances of the libMapper library as managed applications are in the system. The E-MAPPER resource manager maintains an overview of the managed applications and their allocated resources. The E-MAPPER resource manager does not replace a traditional OS scheduler but manages resource allocations and application configurations. It searches and selects new application configurations whenever a new application starts in the system, a running application exits, or system-level triggers occur. The selection process, guided by the application (2) and hardware (1) descriptions, optimizes the resource allocation for individual applications. Section 4 discusses the resource allocation optimization approach. The E-MAPPER resource manager also monitors performance characteristics and power usage of all applications to train and calibrate the application mapping descriptions at runtime, detailed in Section 5.

The libMapper library establishes communication between the global resource manager and individual applications and applies the configuration selected by the E-MAPPER manager. Our system uses protobuf¹ messages over Unix sockets for a flexible and extensible communication interface.

¹<https://github.com/protocolbuffers/protobuf>

Figure 3. Typical control flow between a managed application and the E-MAPPER resource manager.

How the configuration is applied in a specific application depends heavily on the application type and its available level of elasticity, discussed in Section 3.2.

A typical control flow between a managed application and the E-MAPPER resource manager is shown in Figure 3. At application startup, the libMapper library initializes, registers with the resource manager, and reads the application description file, which contains an application identifier and the list of operating points. Additionally, the library performs checks on the application binary to identify potential configuration options. The collected information is transmitted to the E-MAPPER manager, which thereon reevaluates the current system load and resource allocations and selects new configurations for all managed applications. These selected configurations are communicated back to the individual application libraries, which adapt the applications accordingly. Hence, the libMapper library responsible for the newly started application (App₁ in the figure) also receives an `activate_config` message and performs the initial application configuration. Such messages can occur anytime during an application’s lifetime, potentially reconfiguring the application multiple times over the course of its execution.

3.2 E-MAPPER Application Types

E-MAPPER distinguishes between different types of applications to optimally manage them within a heterogeneous processor. The main difference between the types lies in the adaption options available to each type. Determining the correct application type is done by the libMapper library during startup or specified in the application’s description file.

Static Applications. Applications without identified runtime adaptation mechanisms are labeled as *static*. Static applications are allocated to specific cores at runtime, always according to an operating point selected by the manager. Depending on the application description, the libMapper library might allocate specific application threads to individual cores or restrict the entire application to a subset of available processor cores. If applications run with more threads than the cores allocated by E-MAPPER, the possible parallelism will be lower as threads will have to time-multiplex the same processor core.

Scalable Applications. The libMapper library searches for supported runtime libraries for adaptive execution, such as Intel TBB, OpenMP, and TensorFlow. If such libraries are used, the application is marked as *scalable*. E-MAPPER can dynamically scale applications when resource allocations change. For example, if an application is reallocated to two E-cores on an Intel Raptor Lake system, the libMapper library not only adapts the CPU affinity but also instructs the runtime library to use two threads, allowing applications to better adapt to new configurations and reduce the interference due to resource overutilization.

Custom Applications. Application developers can provide their own extensions to support more application configuration options. For instance, we implemented a libMapper library extension that enables application-specific scaling for Kahn Process Networks (KPN) [31]. Instead of generically scaling the number of threads, this extension scales specific *parallel regions* inside the application, leaving other parts unmodified. This allows fine-grained resource allocations for different application phases.

Future work could investigate further extensions that react to the allocated resources, such as using different algorithms or specialized code paths within the application or handling ISA-extension differences between core types. These configurations need to be application-specific and provided by the developer. Our libMapper provides an interface to extend communication with the E-MAPPER manager, easily supporting application-specific adaptations.

3.3 E-MAPPER within the System Stack

E-MAPPER aims to extend the current system stack rather than replace an existing component. E-MAPPER relies on OS components such as the scheduler or performance and

power monitoring. E-MAPPER’s core responsibility requires a holistic view of the system, similar to modern system management daemons such as systemd, OpenRC, and launchd, we envision E-MAPPER to play a central role within user-space management. Hardware description files (①) would be provided by the system manufacturer or distribution while application description files (②) would be shipped together with the applications. Managing these description files in a central file hierarchy would allow a well-defined and user-extensible configuration database, enabling easy adjustments and powerful resource management by E-MAPPER.

Making Applications E-MAPPER-ready. To achieve the best results with E-MAPPER, applications should be equipped with a description file tailored to the hardware they run on. For static or scalable applications supported by libMapper out-of-the-box, no further adjustments are needed. The library automatically identifies if the application can be dynamically adapted and reconfigures it at runtime accordingly. Custom application support, like for KPNs, requires changes to the application itself for proper E-MAPPER-integration. If an application lacks a description file or has an incomplete one, E-MAPPER can automatically learn the application’s behavior at runtime. The *Online Configuration Refinement* algorithm is described in detail in Section 5.

4 E-MAPPER Resource Allocation

The core challenge addressed by E-MAPPER is the optimal allocation of resources to applications. Thus E-MAPPER’s algorithm is designed to balance the resource needs of applications with overall system energy efficiency.

4.1 System Model

In E-MAPPER, a platform is equipped with a *heterogeneous processor* \mathcal{P} with m core types, represented as the vector $\mathcal{P}[\vec{\Theta}] = [\Theta_1, \dots, \Theta_m]^T$. Each core type, while sharing the same Instruction Set Architecture (ISA), exhibits distinct performance-energy characteristics and may have varying hardware properties such as different ISA extensions or the number of supported hardware threads. Since performance and energy characteristics of the multi-threaded cores also vary depending on number of used hardware threads, our algorithm ensures that applications are isolated at the core level, thus do not share sibling hardware threads.

When an application σ connects to E-MAPPER, it sends an application description containing a list of *operating points* $\sigma[\Phi]$. Each operating point $\sigma[\phi_i] \in \sigma[\Phi]$ is defined by the required resources $\vec{\theta}$, (normalized) utility v , and average power consumption ρ , i.e., $\sigma[\phi] = \phi(\vec{\theta}, v, \rho)$. Resource requirements are specified at the core level; if an operating point uses multiple hardware threads of a single processor core, this core is counted only once in $\phi[\vec{\theta}]$. Operating points

are assumed to be Pareto-filtered, meaning each point is better than any other in at least one parameter, such as fewer cores of a particular core type θ_k , higher utility v , or lower power consumption ρ .

For each operating point, E-MAPPER calculates the *energy-utility cost* $\phi[\zeta]$, an adaptation of the traditional Energy-Delay Product (EDP) formula designed to balance energy efficiency with the performance impact of applications [39, 44]. Assuming that utility is inversely proportional to delay, the energy-utility cost is defined as follows:

$$\phi[\zeta] = \left(\frac{\phi[\rho]}{\phi[v]} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\phi[v]} \right) \quad (1)$$

4.2 Optimization Problem

The E-MAPPER resource allocation algorithm selects one operating point per application in a way that minimizes the overall system energy-utility cost. This optimization problem can be formulated as:

$$\mathbf{minimize} \quad \sum_{\sigma \in \Sigma} \sigma[\phi^*][\zeta], \quad (2a)$$

$$\mathbf{subject\ to} \quad \sum_{\sigma \in \Sigma} \sigma[\phi^*][\vec{\theta}] \leq \mathcal{P}[\vec{\Theta}]. \quad (2b)$$

Equation (2a) minimizes the sum of the energy-utility costs of each application’s selected operating points. The constraint in Equation (2b) ensures that the total resource demand from all selected operating points does not exceed the available resources for each processor core type.

This optimization problem is equivalent to the *multiple choice multi-dimensional knapsack problem* (MMKP) [38]. In MMKP, all items have a *scalar* value and a *multi-dimensional* weight, and they are divided into several groups. The goal is to select a single item from each group (*multiple-choice*) so that the overall value is maximized and the overall weight does not exceed the maximum allowed weight at each dimension.

In our optimization problem, each application’s operating points represent items in a group. The goal is to select one operating point per application (one item per group) such that the overall value is minimized. Here, the *weight* is the number of used processors of each type, and the *value* of the item is represented as a negative energy-utility cost.

Given that MMKP is NP-hard [48], finding an optimal solution within a reasonable time, especially for a large number of applications and operating points, is computationally challenging. Since our resource allocation algorithm is used at runtime, E-MAPPER employs a state-of-the-art approximate algorithm based on Lagrangian relaxation, which solves the optimization problem with relaxed constraints and then selects the resultant operating points that fulfill the resource constraints. The detailed description of the algorithm is provided in [67, 68].

Limitations. It is possible that the resource allocation algorithm does not find any suitable operating point for some of the applications due to prior allocations. This situation may occur if the number of managed applications exceeds the number of available resources. In such cases, E-MAPPER temporarily relaxes the constraint in Equation (2b), allowing applications to execute in co-allocation. Since co-allocation adversely affects the performance of the co-allocated applications, E-MAPPER does not perform performance monitoring, as discussed in the next section.

5 Exploring Operating Points at Runtime

Traditionally, operating points for HAM approaches have been generated at design time, leveraging substantial computational resources to identify Pareto-optimal configurations [47]. However, in practical PC scenarios, the operating system may not have predefined operating points, or the available ones might be imprecise due to variations in hardware, despite using similar architectures. Runtime exploration of operating points represents a synergy between Design Space Exploration (DSE) and Runtime Resource Management. This integration poses several challenges, primarily the need to identify effective operating points quickly. Once identified, the algorithm continues refining the Pareto front as new measurements become available.

During exploration, online measurements determine the utility and power consumption of the running applications. If applications do not provide their own utility metrics, we use Instructions Per Second (IPS) as a generic measure of utility. Performance metrics, such as IPS and power, are not constants; they fluctuate due to measurement noise and varying application stages. This variability requires periodic re-evaluation to ensure the robustness and reliability of solutions. Furthermore, the search for near-optimal configurations must be seamlessly integrated within the runtime resource management of the E-MAPPER manager. This integration ensures that while exploring new operating points, the selected configurations do not compete with other concurrently running applications on processor cores. It also requires that the resource management algorithm allocates sufficient resources to new applications, allowing them substantial solution space for exploration without significantly undermining the performance of existing applications.

To address these challenges, we have enhanced the resource allocation algorithm in E-MAPPER to include the exploration of operating points directly during application execution. This process involves continuous performance monitoring and employing a regression model to dynamically adjust operating points, ensuring robust, Pareto-optimal configurations. Our algorithm effectively balances new operating point exploration with efficient resource allocation, optimizing overall system performance.

Figure 4. Evaluation of several regression models in terms of Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) for IPS and Power (lower is better), Inverted Generational Distance (IGD) (lower is better), and the ratio of common operating points in the Pareto-front (higher is better) across 15 different applications on the Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K.

5.1 Runtime Performance and Power Monitoring

Accurate monitoring of runtime performance metrics is essential for a good approximation of Pareto fronts. To reliably measure performance values such as IPS, we employ the Linux performance monitoring subsystem `perf2`, which allows monitoring various performance-related hardware and software metrics, such as retired instructions, cache misses, etc. With the proper configuration, `perf` automatically multiplexes measurements for different applications.

For assessing power consumption, we use built-in power sensors available in modern systems, such as the RAPL (Running Average Power Limit) counters on Intel machines. However, these sensors generally measure the total energy consumption of the system rather than per application. To address this challenge, we build atop `EnergAt` [24], which monitors RAPL counters alongside the execution metrics of each thread across the hardware threads.

Since `EnergAt` does not support different core types in heterogeneous CPUs, we introduce power coefficients between core types ($P^P = \gamma \cdot P^E$, determined statically) to attribute total energy consumption (E_{Δ}^{CPU}) to P-cores (E_{Δ}^P) and E-cores (E_{Δ}^E):

$$E_{\Delta}^{CPU} = E_{\Delta}^P + E_{\Delta}^E = T_{total}^P \cdot P^P + T_{total}^E \cdot P^E \quad (3)$$

where $T_{total}^{P|E}$ is the sum of CPU time for all threads running on P-cores and E-cores, respectively. After approximating E_{Δ}^P and E_{Δ}^E values, we can employ the `EnergAt` methodology to further attribute energy to the applications running on homogeneous subsets of cores.

Considering the inherent variability in measured IPS and power, we implement an exponential moving average (EMA)

to stabilize these metrics, accommodating recognition of changes in application stages and their corresponding power and performance characteristics. The EMA is updated as follows:

$$value_{new} = value_{measured} \cdot \alpha + value_{old} \cdot (1 - \alpha) \quad (4)$$

where α (E-MAPPER uses 0.1) is a smoothing factor. This formula smooths short-term fluctuations while adapting to significant shifts in application behavior, ensuring accurate and responsive performance and power profiling.

5.2 Selection of the Regression Model

We evaluated several regression models for predicting IPS and power consumption for unexplored operating points. Each operating point's configuration is characterized with a vector that includes the number of cores of each type and their hardware thread usage. For instance, on the Intel Raptor Lake platform, the configuration vector includes the number of E-cores, P-cores using one hardware thread, and P-cores using both hardware threads. The models assessed were Polynomial Regression (degrees 1 to 3), Neural Networks (NN), and Support Vector Machines (SVM). We used pre-measured configurations across 15 applications on the Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K as the data sets. Each model was evaluated using training subsets of different sizes across 10 randomly generated seeds for robustness.

The first two plots in Figure 4 show the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) for predicted IPS and power values. Polynomial regression models improved in accuracy for both IPS and power as the training size increased. Higher-degree polynomial models achieved greater accuracy at larger training sizes, albeit requiring more data points to converge. Conversely, NN and SVM models performed better in predicting

²Most of its functionality is provided by the system call `perf_event_open`.

power values at larger training sizes but were significantly worse in predicting IPS compared to polynomial models.

Furthermore, we compare the predicted Pareto fronts with a reference Pareto front (derived from the measured configurations) using Inverted Generational Distance (IGD) [14] and the ratio of common operating points. IGD measures the average distance from points on the reference Pareto front to the nearest point on the generated front, assessing the coverage of the generated front relative to the reference one. The bottom two plots in Figure 4 show that polynomial models consistently outperformed SVM and NN in aligning with the reference Pareto front. Particularly, polynomial regression models of degrees 2 and 3 outperformed the first-degree model in approximating the reference front. Both second and third-degree models produced similar accuracy, but the second-degree model was more efficient, requiring only 20 training points to generate robust Pareto fronts. Based on this efficiency, we selected the second-degree polynomial regression model for our runtime exploration approach.

5.3 Runtime Exploration Algorithm Design

As discussed earlier, it is critical to integrate the runtime exploration of operating points seamlessly into the resource allocation algorithm. The chosen points for measurement should not overlap with processor cores used by concurrently running applications. Simultaneously, the resource allocation algorithm should allocate sufficient resources to ensure effective exploration without adversely affecting the performance of other applications.

We categorize the maturity of an application’s operating points into three stages: (1) *Initial* stage, where there are insufficient measured operating points making approximations unreliable; (2) *Refinement* stage, characterized by an intermediate number of measured points but still limited accuracy in approximations; and (3) *Stable* stage, at which sufficient operating points have been explored, enabling reliable approximations.

Upon invocation, the resource allocation algorithm, as detailed in Section 4, generates the current Pareto front using both measured and approximated operating points. This allocation determines the set of cores assigned to each application. If there are unassigned cores, the exploration algorithm allocates these to applications in the Initial and Refinement stages, allowing them to explore a broader configuration space. Applications in the Stable stage execute on the designated cores provided by the resource allocation algorithm without further configuration adjustments. For applications in the Initial and Refinement stages, specific exploration techniques are employed within the set of remaining cores:

In the *Initial* stage, the selection heuristic for the next operating point is based on the configuration vector, choosing the configuration furthest from the measured configurations to maximize exploration diversity. In the *Refinement* stage, the heuristic is based on approximated IPS and power values

and uses an auxiliary regression, which includes a "zero" configuration (zero power and zero IPS) to anchor the model. The heuristic selects configurations based on the largest discrepancies between the main and the auxiliary regression models. These discrepancies are calculated as the geometric mean of the relative differences in IPS and power values. If both models predict negative IPS or power values for some configurations, discrepancies are calculated relative to a zero value to increase the likelihood of measuring configurations that exhibit such anomaly predictions. After a fixed number of measurements, the exploration process repeats until the application progresses to the *Stable* stage. When applications are in the Stable stage, the resource allocation algorithm is invoked again after a larger number of measurements to reassess the current allocation and potentially switch to another one.

6 Evaluation

To demonstrate that E-MAPPER enhances the management of energy-aware tasks on heterogeneous processors, we conducted an extensive evaluation on two different systems. We explicitly choose systems with distinct characteristics to underline that our approach is generic and works across various types of heterogeneous hardware.

6.1 Evaluation Setup

We evaluate our approach on an Arm-based Odroid XU3-E board [22]. The board features a Samsung Exynos 5422 processor, which implements an Arm big.LITTLE architecture with two core islands, a four-core A15 (big) island and a four-core A7 (LITTLE) island. The system is equipped with 2 GB of memory and energy sensors for the core islands, the memory, and the integrated graphics card. We run a custom-compiled Linux 6.6 kernel on the board, with full support for the Linux Energy-Aware-Scheduler (EAS), a Linux’ built-in optimized application placement strategy [16, 45].

The second system is an Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K, one of Intel’s latest heterogeneous processors. It consists of 8 high-performance P-cores, each supporting SMT, and 16 energy-efficient E-cores that do not support SMT. The system is equipped with 128 GB of memory. For energy measurements, we use the integrated RAPL counters, which have been proven accurate in fine-grained energy measurements [15, 21, 25, 56, 61].

We run a custom-compiled Linux 6.4 kernel, based on the default Debian Testing kernel version, extended with a patch-set adding preliminary support for Intel Thread Director (ITD) [42]. We further extended the patch-set to make the ITD classification of threads and the reference IPC per class determined by the hardware available to user-space. Inspired by Saez et al. [52] we implemented a version of E-MAPPER that uses ITD classifications to allocate processor cores to application threads.

For both platforms we use the performance frequency governor and limit the maximum frequencies to prevent thermal throttling, allowing the cores to run at maximum frequencies for the entire benchmark execution. On the Raptor Lake system, we selected 4.6 GHz for the P-cores and 3.8 GHz for the E-cores, while on the Odroid system, we chose 1.2 GHz for the LITTLE and 1.8 GHz for the big cores.

6.2 Benchmarks

We use different sets of applications to evaluate the features of E-MAPPER. To test dynamic adaptability, we use the OpenMP implementations of the NAS Parallel Benchmarks [6], version 3.4.2. Since the Intel platform is more powerful than the Odroid board, we use different classes of the benchmarks for each system: class *A* for Odroid and class *C* for Intel.

On the Intel Raptor Lake platform, we also evaluate a selection of Intel Thread Building Blocks (Intel TBB) [46] benchmarks and two TensorFlow [19] applications. We chose the benchmarks *binpack*, *fractal*, *parallel-preorder*, *pi*, *primes*, and *seismic* from the official Intel TBB repository as they cover a wide spectrum of the building blocks of the framework. TensorFlow, an open-source framework for machine-learning algorithms, is also included in our evaluation. We implemented a E-MAPPER-enabled version of TensorFlow Lite [2] that can dynamically scale its parallelism at runtime. We evaluate two models, VGG [58] and AlexNet [33], used for image recognition.

Additionally, we use two embedded KPN applications to test the custom extensions of E-MAPPER: *mandelbrot* for calculating the Mandelbrot set [31], and *lms* implementing Leighton-Micali Signatures [41]. Both applications are used in two versions: one with a static application topology (annotated with *static*) and another with implicit data-parallelism in KPNs [31], used to demonstrate dynamic adaptation. Since KPN applications are targeted to embedded platforms, we chose to evaluate them only on the Odroid system.

6.3 Intel Raptor Lake

For our first experiment, we measure the execution of our selected benchmark collection on the Raptor Lake system. We evaluate both single benchmarks and parallel executions of multiple benchmarks. Every scenario is executed with resource management by E-MAPPER and ITD-based resource allocation as described earlier. With E-MAPPER, we use application description files generated from a design space exploration prior to the actual measurement. The ITD-based allocation does not require this step, instead uses hardware-provided classification information for resource allocation. We also measure scenarios using the Linux built-in work-distribution techniques as a baseline.

For each scenario, we record the overall execution time (makespan) and total energy consumption. Each scenario

is measured ten times, and the average results are reported. Figure 5 shows the results for all benchmarks, including geometric means for single application scenarios, multiple application scenarios, and all scenarios combined. The results are presented as improvement factors over the baseline; an improvement factor above 1 indicates faster execution or lower energy consumption, while below 1 indicates the opposite.

Single Application. For single application scenarios, benchmarks generally benefit from being managed by E-MAPPER. The geometric mean improvement factor for E-MAPPER is 1.11 for execution time and 1.57 for energy consumption. There are two notable cases to highlight. First, the *binpack* benchmark from Intel TBB shows a $10\times$ higher IPS with low thread counts. E-MAPPER leverages this behavior by scaling the application accordingly, while the baseline and ITD-based manager cannot, thus resulting in extreme improvement. Second, benchmarks *is*, *sp*, and *parallel-preorder* run longer with E-MAPPER but consume less energy due to E-MAPPER’s optimization algorithm, which balances power consumption and utility.

The ITD-based resource allocation shows only minor differences from the baseline, with overall improvement factors of 1.01 for execution time and 1.04 for energy consumption. ITD improves the *ua* and TensorFlow *vgg* benchmarks by allocating P-cores to more active threads. However, it misclassifies threads for *alexnet*, leading to suboptimal performance.

Multiple Applications. For scenarios with multiple applications running in parallel, E-MAPPER provides significant benefits. The average improvement factor is 1.62 for execution time and 1.81 for energy consumption. Most applications show improvements, with few exceptions matching the baseline.

Managing resources based on ITD information did not yield the expected improvements. Most scenarios only achieved similar performance to the baseline, resulting in an overall improvement factor of 0.95 for execution time and 0.98 for energy consumption when multiple applications ran in parallel. Some minor improvements were observed in scenarios like *is* and *lu* running in parallel, and when five applications run simultaneously. However, combinations like *vgg* and *ft* and *primes* showed worse results, highlighting classification issues.

6.4 Odroid XU3-E

To demonstrate E-MAPPER’s effectiveness on different hardware, we conducted a second experiment on the Odroid XU3-E platform, measuring single and multiple application scenarios. The baseline for this platform uses the Linux Energy-Aware Scheduler (EAS), which leverages the power model of the heterogeneous processor. Figure 6 shows the results of this experiment.

Figure 5. Relative improvement factor E-MAPPER and Intel Thread Director over CFS on the Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K (higher y-value is better). E-MAPPER results are shown as bars, Intel Thread Director results are shown as points.

Figure 6. Relative improvement factor E-MAPPER over EAS on the Odroid XU3-E (higher y-value is better).

Single Application. The results for single OpenMP benchmarks are similar to the Intel Raptor Lake experiment. The applications either perform similarly to the baseline or show improved energy consumption with longer execution times (e.g., ua). The is benchmark shows a significant increase in execution time as well as an energy consumption increase. E-MAPPER picks a sub-optimal configuration for this application leading to this negative effects. In contrast, lu, a long-running benchmark, benefits significantly from E-MAPPER in both energy consumption and execution time.

KPN applications show significant improvements with E-MAPPER. E-MAPPER can successfully use the application knobs to tune the application to the available hardware resources, resulting in lower energy consumption for lms and improvements in both metrics for mandelbrot. The static version of mandelbrot behaves the same as the baseline. The static version of lms behaves similar to ua and shows a lower energy consumption at the cost of a longer makespan. On

average, E-MAPPER improved execution time by a factor of 1.07 and energy consumption by 1.27 for single application scenarios.

Multiple Applications. When running multiple applications in parallel, E-MAPPER significantly enhances overall system performance. The geometric mean improvement factor is 1.20 for execution time and 1.38 for energy consumption. Most scenarios show improvements, with only the combination of ep and ft suffering in execution time and energy consumption compared to the baseline.

6.5 Runtime Exploration of Operating Points

This section demonstrates E-MAPPER’s behavior with runtime exploration of operating points on the Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K across 15 single-application and 15 multi-application scenarios.

Figure 7. Runtime exploration of operating points across 30 different scenarios using the Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K.

Each scenario runs 15 times, starting with no predefined operating points. Subsequent runs use data from prior runs to continue exploration. Applications remain in the initial stage until 6 operating points are measured, move to the refinement stage until 25 operating points with at least 20 measurements each are gathered. The measurement period is 50 ms, discarding the first three measurements after reconfiguration to allow applications to adjust. Figure 7 shows the results. The "Training" stage signifies ongoing exploration in at least one application, while the "Stable" stage indicates all applications start from a stable stage.

Not all scenarios reach the stable stage within 15 executions. While all scenarios with single applications reach the stable stage, the three multi-application scenarios do not. These three scenarios involve short-running applications alongside longer-running ones. We suspect the resource distribution between the exploring and the stable stage applications is the issue; applications in the exploration stages do not get enough resources to progress to the stable stage. We believe that further refinement of the runtime exploration algorithm could reduce the likelihood of such situations.

During the training stages, performance and energy consumption fluctuate, and upon reaching the stable stage, the

results stabilize, though E-MAPPER continues to measure and refine operating points. Results are usually worse than those with offline-generated operating points, but for most single-application scenarios, online training gets close to the original results, indicating that online exploration effectively identifies optimal or near-optimal configurations. In multi-application scenarios, results are generally better than the CFS baseline. A notable exception is the binpack + fractal + parallel-preorder scenario, where runtime measurement and prediction result in poor execution time due to a bad estimation for the binpack benchmark. These negative results suggest that the runtime exploration heuristics could be further improved to find better configuration points.

7 Related Work

Optimizing the mapping of applications onto heterogeneous multi-core systems is a well-known problem in embedded systems [60]. The mapping approaches can be classified by the decision time into static mapping, runtime mapping, and hybrid application mapping techniques.

Static Mapping Approaches. Static mapping approaches are among the most widely studied approaches. In static

mapping, resources are allocated prior to application execution, typically during compile or design time. This approach leverages static code analysis, often supplemented by execution traces, profiling data, and models of the target hardware, to determine the optimal resource allocation.

Various strategies are employed to find optimal static mappings. These include meta-heuristic techniques like evolutionary algorithms for design-space exploration (DSE) [3, 28, 49], as well as formulations of well-known problems, like ILP or SMT, which are solved using dedicated solvers [36]. Additionally, simpler heuristics based on domain-specific knowledge are also used [11, 12, 32, 59].

Since static mappings are specified at design time, they allow for more extensive calculations to find an optimal allocation than any runtime approach. This enables complex analysis methods and can produce binaries that are easy to deploy since they do not necessarily need any runtime support. However, static mapping approaches cannot adapt to dynamic scenarios, such as varying system loads or the presence of other concurrently executing applications.

Dynamic Mapping Approaches. On the other end of the spectrum lie dynamic mapping approaches. In these methods, the decision regarding resource allocation is deferred until runtime, where a simple heuristic typically determines the assignment. In most cases, the mapping decision is also combined with task scheduling within single processing elements (PEs) and embedded within the operating system [9, 70]. As mentioned in the Section 1, modern OS schedulers are evolving to better manage heterogeneous multi-core processors, aiming to improve energy efficiency. These schedulers employ techniques such as using CPU energy models [45] or leveraging hardware-assisted tools such as Intel’s Thread Director [7, 13, 17, 42, 52]. However, dynamic approaches are inherently limited in their optimization space. While they are more adaptive, the applied heuristics must remain lightweight to ensure efficient execution. This requirement often restricts them to operating with limited information.

Hybrid Mapping Approaches. To address the limitations of static and dynamic mapping methods, a trend for *hybrid* application mapping (HAM) approaches has emerged [47]. HAM strategies leverage extensive analyses from static methods at compile time while deferring final decision-making to runtime. This class of approaches ensures efficiency while retaining flexibility to adapt to dynamic system loads. During the design stage, hybrid approaches employ sophisticated DSE methodologies to characterize the impact of different resource allocations on the non-functional properties of the mapping. The outcome of DSE is a set of (possibly incomplete) mapping options, referred to as *operating points*, each characterized by the required amount and type of resources and the obtainable execution properties. Approaches such as [40, 43, 59] use heuristics for efficient exploration of Pareto-optimal configurations, while others [5, 37, 50, 65]

apply evolutionary algorithms. Other approaches also distinguish different application scenarios [50, 53, 55, 62].

At runtime, the resource managers utilize the generated operating points and partition resources among multiple, concurrently executed applications. Algorithms may map applications on the platform one at a time [59, 65], or in a joint manner by formulating the problem via a Multiple-choice Multidimensional Knapsack Problem (MMKP) [38], and using ILP solvers [8], or fast knapsack heuristics based on Pareto algebra principles [57], Lagrangian relaxation [62, 67, 68], or greedy heuristics [69]. Similar approaches are also discussed for cluster scheduling in cloud environments, where the dynamic distribution of jobs in a heterogeneous cloud environment is solved using ILP solvers [63].

The aforementioned approaches generate *spatial* multi-application mappings, i.e., they only generate a mapping for the current running set of applications and do not consider the changes in the workload nor further optimize the execution. To address it, some works [29, 30, 32] proposed generating *spatio-temporal* mappings at runtime instead. However, it is important to note that while these approaches offer significant improvements in terms of energy efficiency and meeting real-time constraints, they often postpone the execution of the application to select the more efficient operating later. Such a strategy, while suitable for real-time systems, is less ideal for regular desktop computers where users expect immediate application responsiveness.

Application Adaptivity. A common limitation in many of the mapping approaches discussed is their focus primarily on thread-to-core pinning, without fully exploiting the adaptability potential of applications. Beyond mere assignment of threads to processor cores, certain applications possess additional *knobs* that allow them to adjust their internal configurations dynamically at runtime. For instance, some applications have the capability to modify their topology, alter the parallelization degree of data-parallel regions, or switch between different internal algorithms based on runtime conditions [31, 54]. Another scaling approach involves distributing work within OpenMP applications in a heterogeneous-hardware aware fashion [51]. Despite these possibilities, modern operating system often fail to leverage these adaptive features, missing opportunities to optimize application performance and resource utilization.

8 Conclusion

This paper introduces E-MAPPER, a resource management system designed for energy-aware applications on heterogeneous processors. E-MAPPER’s key innovations include a uniform interface to a global resource manager for passing high-level application descriptions and an allocation algorithm that balances performance and energy consumption. E-MAPPER supports a broad spectrum of application models, from static to scalable types, and even custom-specific ones

with unique adaptivity features like reconfiguration options and algorithmic variations. Crucially, E-MAPPER does not require detailed knowledge of each application’s adaptivity aspects. Instead, it receives only the essential information needed for efficient resource allocation (resource requirements and non-functional characteristics), with the rest handled on the client side. This flexible design allows for various management scenarios.

Evaluations on two different heterogeneous systems showed that E-MAPPER can significantly improve application execution, both when given exclusive access to resources and when competing with concurrent applications. We reported improvements in terms of execution time and energy consumption of 25 % and 40 % for the Intel Raptor Lake Core i9-13900K and 12 % and 25 % for the Odroid XU3-E. For embedded KPN applications with custom adaptivity knobs, we demonstrated E-MAPPER’s extensibility in providing fine-grained resource adaptations. Finally, we showed that even in the absence of application descriptions, E-MAPPER can efficiently manage unknown applications through its runtime exploration approach, which predicts application behavior based on few samples.

In summary, this work highlights the value of a simple yet effective interface to express application characteristics to the OS. By communicating operating points annotated with resource requirements and non-functional characteristics, E-MAPPER considerably improves the system’s overall energy-awareness. We advocate for the development of a uniform application-resource-manager interface to enhance energy efficiency across diverse applications and systems.

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